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NURHANIFA S. ABOLAIS, MAEd

Instructor III

Mindanao State University - Integrated Laboratory School

Marawi City, Lanao del Sur, Philippines

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Journey from High School to an Unpredictable Destiny

“I want to be a Pharmacist.” That was her goal. Ever since she was young, she dreamed of wearing a white lab coat, helping people, and working in a pharmacy. She did everything she could to make that dream come true. She studied hard, burned the midnight oil, and gave her best to maintain her grades and not fail. Her goal was to graduate from one of the most prestigious secondary schools in her community, the **Mindanao State University – Science Training Center – Science High School**, now known as the **Institute of Science Education**.

People often said that studying there was extremely difficult, that students had no time to breathe and no life outside of books. And they were right. Even during holidays and special events at their university, classes would continue. While others were cheering and enjoying themselves at the grandstand, the students of STC were bent over their notebooks, writing, solving problems, or working on projects as if they couldn't hear the noise around them.

But despite the challenges, she endured. She cried, laughed, and learned. There were sleepless nights, countless quizzes, and moments of doubt, but also memories with classmates that made it all worth it. She pushed herself because she knew she was doing it not only for herself but also for her loving and supportive parents, who always believed in her.

Thanks to their unwavering support, she finally graduated from her dream school. It was one of the proudest moments of her life. All those years of hard work paid off. She was ready to take the next step in college.

When she was accepted as a scholar at **Mindanao State University**, she felt that her dreams were finally taking shape. But life had a different plan. Her dream of becoming a pharmacist slowly faded away when her father didn't allow her to take the Pharmacy course. At that time, the nearest university offering that program was in Cebu, far from home. Her father couldn't bear to let her go that far, worried about her safety and the distance.

She was deeply hurt and disappointed. For years, she had worked so hard for that one dream, and suddenly it felt like everything fell apart. She cried silently, questioning why things turned out that way. But even though her heart was heavy,

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she chose to be strong. She didn't want to disappoint her parents, who only wanted the best for her.

So, she decided to enroll in the **College of Business Administration** at the said university, even if it wasn't what she truly wanted. At first, she felt lost. Everything was new and unfamiliar. But as time went on, she started to see things differently. She met new people, gained confidence, and discovered talents she never knew she had.

Little by little, she realized that things do happen for a reason. Maybe her path wasn't meant to be in the field of medicine, but somewhere else, somewhere she could still grow and make her mark.

Her journey taught her that dreams can change, but that doesn't mean giving up. Sometimes, life leads us to places we never planned to go, not to break us, but to help us find where we truly belong.